

MEASUREMENT OF BOND OF FRP COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT IN CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A probe has been designed for the measurement of internal strains in fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) reinforcement for concrete structures, enabling the characterization of the FRP/concrete bond. The probe is used to measure strain distributions during the direct pullout of FRP rods embedded in a cube of concrete. The probe's capabilities and some initial results on the characterization of bond are presented. It is shown that it is feasible to develop a finite element model of the bond based on load-slip data, and that the model is capable of predicting the rod's strain distribution along the embedment length during pullout.

INTRODUCTION

One of the primary concerns of designers wishing to use FRP reinforced concrete is the long-term durability of the structure. In particular, there is a question about the durability of the FRP itself and the efficiency of FRP as a reinforcement. In bonded FRP reinforcement (prestressed or non-prestressed), the main issue in reinforcement efficiency concerns the bond between rod and concrete. That is, there must be an adequate bond to enable anchorage of the reinforcement to the concrete within a reasonable length. Hence, the strength and durability of the bond during a projected 50-year lifetime becomes an important research issue since inadequate information of this sort is currently available [1].

Although the accepted means of determining bond stresses in steel reinforcement is to split a reinforcing bar, install strain gages on the split surface, and epoxy the bar back together [2], this is impractical for FRP due to dimensional and material restrictions. The objective of the present investigation is to develop a method of characterizing the FRP/concrete bond in laboratory specimens. These specimens are to be used in a broader investigation at Penn State University (PSU) on the development of accelerated test methods for the evaluation of long term bond in FRP reinforced structures, and were designed with simplicity and functionality in mind. To that end, the main features of the test are that it is simple to model, it enables the easy measurement of slip of the rod, and it allows for the measurement of stress transfer between the reinforcement and the concrete. The focus of this paper is on the design, verification, and use of an internal strain probe for the sensing of strain distribution inside the rod. From this distribution, one can calculate how load is transferred between the reinforcement rod and the concrete. The potential degradation of this load transfer mechanism in the presence of aggressive environmental factors

is of great importance and needs to be determined before the use of FRP reinforcement in concrete structures becomes commonplace.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The pultruded, circular-sectioned FRP rods used in this investigation were manufactured by DFI, Inc. (Erlanger, KY) and in-house at PSU. The vinylester (DFI) and polyester (PSU) rods had smooth, as-received finishes and diameters of 12.7 and 10 mm, respectively. While the smooth surface profile of the rods was chosen for simplicity in measuring and modeling the strain measuring capability of the probe, commercial rods will most likely have contoured surface profiles and rough coatings to improve bonding with concrete.

The specimen used to characterize the FRP/concrete bond consisted of a single FRP rod embedded in a 150-mm-cube of high early strength concrete (Fig. 1). A direct pullout load was applied to one end of the rod until gross slipping at the unloaded end of the rod occurred [3]. Slip distances at both ends of the rod were each monitored with three LVDTs. An embedment length of ten rod diameters was ensured by the bond breakers shown in Fig. 1. A fundamental aspect of this specimen design is that the FRP controlled the pullout behavior; the concrete never failed [3,4]. Hence, the effect of the environmental degradation of the FRP on bond can be isolated in future work.

The need for an internal strain sensing probe arises from the need to avoid disturbing the FRP/concrete bond with strain sensing devices on the surface of the rod. While surface mounted strain gages [5] and internal optical fiber strain sensors [6] have been used in the past with FRP rods in concrete, it was felt that an effective, disposable, internal probe that did not disturb in the FRP/concrete interface could be easily fabricated in-house. The configuration decided upon was a thin aluminum tube (3.9-mm OD, 3.2-mm ID) that can be instrumented with several longitudinal and/or transverse strain gages at several positions along its length. For the initial phase of this investigation, longitudinal strain gages on the probe were located at various positions within the bonded length of the rod. A 5.6 mm dia. hole was drilled longitudinally through the embedded length of the rod to accommodate the probe and a layer of epoxy.

Experimental verification of the accuracy of the probe design entailed monotonic and cyclic tensile loading of the stand alone FRP rod instrumented with a probe and strain gages on the OD of the rod. Loads were introduced by mechanical grips with two- or four-piece wedges described in [7]. Two main objectives of these tests were to assure that the gages on the probe accurately reflected strains on the surface of the rod and that the measurements were repeatable. Once the probe verification in stand alone FRP was accomplished, pull-out tests using an FRP rod with a probe and OD-mounted strain gages were carried out to determine whether or not the distributed shear loading mode encountered in the embedment length would cause discrepancies between the probe and surface strain measurements.

ANALYSIS METHOD

The pullout specimen as well as stand alone FRP with a probe were modeled using a 3-D, axisymmetric finite element analysis with the ANSYS software package. The concrete cube was modeled as an equal-volume cylinder. Strains predicted from the analysis of probe/FRP and probe/FRP/concrete specimens were compared with corresponding experimental results. The model of the probe/FRP/concrete specimen is shown in Fig. 2; the model of the probe/FRP was

similar except for the lack of concrete. The concrete, aluminum, and epoxy adhesive were all modeled as linear elastic and isotropic. The FRP was linear elastic and transversely isotropic.

To model slipping between FRP and concrete, gap elements were used in conjunction with nonlinear springs that resisted relative shear displacement between nodes on opposite sides of the gap (Fig. 3). It was determined early on that the two most important gap parameters are the initial interference of the gap elements, i.e. the initial radial compression at the interface, and the expression for the nonlinear shear spring. This interference was found to correlate closely with the load required to initiate slip at the free end of the rod, and a value of $2.1 \mu\text{m}$ provided the best agreement with the pullout test data. The nonlinear shear spring expression influenced the overall shape of the load-slip diagram curve, and the best expression to match the data was found to be $F = 2 \exp(-200d)$, where F is the shear force in Newtons and d is the relative shear displacement of adjacent nodes, in meters. Once determined, these gap parameters would then be used to predict the distribution of longitudinal strain in the FRP rod which, in turn, would be verified with additional experimental data. The remaining gap constants from Fig. 3 were as follows: $K_n=175 \text{ MN/m}$, $K_s=17.5 \text{ MN/m}$, $\mu=1$. The normal the shear spring constants were chosen to be substantially higher than the surrounding material stiffnesses, and the coefficient of friction was a best engineering estimate.

RESULTS

Initial experiments were aimed at determining the extent of the shear lag zone at the tip of the probe in a stand alone FRP rod. Figure 4 shows the location of the gages in a glass/polyester rod subjected to tension from the ends, and Fig. 5 compares the strain measurements for two unequal tensile load excursions. Note that all gages except that on the solid section of the rod and that close to probe tip (P1) are in excellent agreement. The respective reasons these two gages read lower are that (a) the solid section strain should be about 16% less than the others due to the higher stiffness in this portion of the rod and (b) gage P1 is located within the shear lag region of the probe. Finite element results not included here suggested that probe and surface strains measured at least 12 mm from the tip of the probe are in close agreement. Based on these results, all probe strain gages were located at least 12 mm from the tip of the probe.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the probe inside the embedded length, experiments were carried out with a glass/polyester rod instrumented with an internal probe and strain gages on the OD of the rod (Fig. 6). The distance between the loaded-end bond breaker and the nearest strain gage was 18 mm. A plot of nominal bond stress (load divided by embedment area) versus the gage readings indicated excellent agreement between the gages nearest the loaded end, and fair agreement between the remaining gages (Fig. 7). It can also be seen that the range of the probe gages was greater than that of the rod gages since the latter failed prematurely due to abrasion with the concrete. Note that once loading commenced much of the rod experienced a complicated strain gradient that could only be measured internally.

To demonstrate the utility of the internal strain probe, two representative experiments are included in the sequel. These experiments were carried out using glass/vinylester rods containing probes. The nonlinear spring constant and the initial interference in the finite element model were calibrated based on the slip data (Fig. 8). The agreement between analysis and data in Fig. 8 is acceptable, although this should be expected since the gap constants were chosen to fit the data. After the two primary constants in the model were obtained, predictions of longitudinal strain were made and compared to experimental data in Fig. 9. The good agreement between data and analysis indicates that the fundamental nature of the bond mechanism has been captured by the model. This result is particularly important in light of the method followed to make the

prediction; i.e., based on *external* measurements (slip), the *internal* strain distribution and thereby bond stress distribution were successfully predicted.

CONCLUSION

Based on the work summarized above, the standard probe configuration decided upon for subsequent experiments is one where the minimum distance between the tip of the probe and a strain gage is 12 mm. This minimizes undesirable shear lag between the exterior and interior of the rod. The probe has been shown to faithfully reproduce exterior strains in the rod even when the rod is loaded by shear transfer in the embedment length.

The finite element model incorporating gap elements with nonlinear springs is capable of modeling both the load-slip and load-strain behavior of the FRP reinforcement in concrete during direct pullout tests. The most important gap constants that need to be determined based on load-slip curves are the initial interference and the nonlinear shear spring constant. The former is most important in predicting the proper load at free-end slip, while the latter is more important in capturing the overall shape of the load-slip diagram. The salient result reported in this paper is that internal strain distributions in FRP reinforcement can be predicted based on measurements of external slip. Additional research will aim to refine this capability and utilize it to investigate effect of accelerated aging on bond in FRP reinforced concrete.

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Figure 1. Illustration of direct pullout test [3].

Figure 2. Axisymmetric finite element model of the probe, FRP, and concrete.

Figure 3. Gap element properties.

Figure 4. Layout of strain gages on glass/polyester rod with probe.

Figure 5. Strain vs. load for strain gages shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 6. Layout of strain gages on glass/polyester rod with probe, in concrete.

Figure 7. Probe and rod OD strain distributions measured with gages shown in Fig. 6. All dimensions in mm. Drawing not to scale.

Figure 8. Predicted and measured slip in two glass/vinylester pullout tests.

Figure 9. Predicted and measured strain distributions in pullout tests of Fig. 8. Dimensions in mm refer to distances between strain gages and loaded end bond breaker.